

ELASTO-PLASTIC BEHAVIOUR OF SHORT FIBER REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a General Self-Consistent Finite Element Iterative Averaging Method, which is a general procedure for evaluation of local fields and overall responses of short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites. The effects of micro-structural characteristics, e.g. the fiber's volume fraction and aspect ratio, and the fiber-to-fiber ends spacing etc., on the macroscopic elasto-plastic behaviour of short fiber reinforced SiC/Al composite, for a typical material, are studied. By the analysis of microscopic stress fields of the composite, it could be found that the propagation and distribution of elasto-plastic deformation in the matrix would affect considerably the macroscopic response of the composite.

INTRODUCTION

Ductile metals (Aluminium or the other alloys) reinforced with SiC/Al particles or whiskers could constitute the composites with high specific stiffness and strength. In addition, such composites, which have the advantages of low cost and good mechanical and workable properties, have been widely used in the engineering structures.

Because the composites are reinforced discontinuously, the mechanical properties of the matrix alloy and the microstructure of the composites play an important role in the overall properties of the composites. Christman et al[1], by analyzing the effects of reinforcements geometry, volume fraction and clustering as well as matrix microstructure on the elasto-plastic deformation behaviour of metal matrix composites, pointed out that the composite strengthening is directly related to the triaxiality and constrained plastic flow in the matrix due to the presence of brittle reinforcements. Papazian et al [2,3] studied the effects of age hardening factors of aluminium alloy matrix on the overall tensile properties, and concluded that the increment in strength obtainable by the age hardening is usually equal to or even greater than that due to the SiC addition. However, since the microstructure of such composites is not only complicated but also subtle, there haven't got the complete recognition of how it effects the overall mechanical properties of the composites by far.

The Periodic Array (PA) model [1,3-6] and Self-Consistent (SC) method [7,8] are often used to predict the elastic and elasto-plastic properties of the metal matrix composite. As Christman et al [1] pointed out, the boundary conditions of the " representative element's side wall constraint" in

PA model results in overestimating the flow stress values of the composites, which was also shown in reference [3]. And, the whiskers are assumed as ellipsoidal inclusions in the SC method, which couldn't take account of the effects of phase's geometrical configurations. In order to overcome the weak points above, the authors, basing on the previous work [9], developed a Generalized Self-Consistent Finite Element Iterative Averaging Method (GSCFEIAM) [10]. The generalized self-consistent model is united with the finite element method, and through the averaging procedure to the non-uniform stress fields, strain fields and the non-uniform nonlinear physical states in each phase, the overall effective properties of the composites are derived iteratively. So the traditional generalized self-consistent method is extended to dispose of the nonlinear deformation problems of the composites with complicated microstructures.

The present paper, based on the GSCFEIAM, studies the elasto-plastic tensile properties of SiC particles or whiskers reinforced Aluminium- matrix composites. And, the propagation and distribution of the microscopic plastic region in the matrix are investigated to analyze the overall elasto-plastic deformation process of the composites.

GENERALIZED SELF-CONSISTENT FINITE ELEMENT ITERATIVE AVERAGING METHOD

Generally, we assume that each phase of the composite is in the elasto-plastic deformation stage. Its local stress field (or strain field) is not only non-uniform but related to the loading history. The incremental stress field of each phase could be written as:

$$d\bar{\sigma}_r(x,t) = A_r(x, \sigma(t))d\bar{\sigma}(t) \tag{1}$$

where the subscript r represents the phase, that is $r = f$ indicates the fiber phase, while $r = m$ indicates the matrix phase, A_r is the local concentration tensor. The incremental stress-strain relation is

$$d\bar{\epsilon}_r = S_r^{ep}(x, \bar{\sigma}(t))d\bar{\sigma}_r(x,t) \tag{2}$$

Here S_r^{ep} is the local elasto-plastic compliance tensor. The volume averages of local stress and strain field are defined by

$$d\bar{\sigma}_r(t) = \frac{1}{V_r} \int_{V_r} A_r(x, \bar{\sigma}(t))d\bar{\sigma}(t)dv \equiv \bar{A}_r(\bar{\sigma}(t))d\bar{\sigma}(t) \tag{3}$$

$$d\bar{\epsilon}_r(t) = \frac{1}{V_r} \int_{V_r} S_r^{ep}(x, \bar{\sigma}(t))d\bar{\sigma}_r(x,t)dv \equiv \bar{S}_r^{ep}(\bar{\sigma}(t))d\bar{\sigma}_r(t) \tag{4}$$

where \bar{A}_r and \bar{S}_r^{ep} are the average incremental stress concentration tensor and the elasto-plastic compliance tensor, respectively, and

$$\bar{S}_r^{ep}(\bar{\sigma}(t)) = \left[\frac{1}{V_r} \int_{V_r} S_r^{ep}(x, \bar{\sigma}(t))d\bar{\sigma}_r(x,t)dv \right] d\bar{\sigma}_r(t) / \left[d\bar{\sigma}_r^T(t)d\bar{\sigma}_r(t) \right] \tag{5}$$

For the ductile metals reinforced by brittle particles or whiskers case, from Eqn(3) and (4), the overall incremental elasto-plastic properties of the composites can be written as:

$$S_c^{ep} = \bar{S}_m^{ep} + V_f(S_f - \bar{S}_m^{ep})\bar{A}_f \tag{6}$$

Here, V_f is the fiber's volume fraction; S_c^{ep} is the overall incremental elasto-plastic compliance tensor of the composites, and S_f is the fiber's elastic compliance tensor.

Furthermore, we confine our attentions to the elasto-plastic tensile properties of the composites. Then, Eqn(6) can be reduced to

$$1/E_c^{ep} = 1/\bar{E}_m^{ep} + V_f(1/E_f - 1/\bar{E}_m^{ep})a_f \quad (7)$$

where E_f is the fiber's Young's modulus; E_c^{ep} and \bar{E}_m^{ep} are the incremental tensile modulus of the composites and the matrix, respectively; and a_f is the component of \bar{A}_f . In addition,

$$\bar{E}_m^{ep} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{E_m} + \frac{d\bar{\epsilon}_m^p}{d\bar{\sigma}_m}} \quad (8)$$

where E_m is the Young's modulus of the matrix; while $d\bar{\sigma}_m$ and $d\bar{\epsilon}_m^p$ are, respectively, the average incremental Von-Mises effective stress and plastic strain of the matrix.

By the computational auxiliary model [9] and the basic iterative steps of GSCFEIAM [10], the stress - strain response can be derived. The finite element mesh for GSCFEIAM is shown in Fig.1.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The elasto-plastic tensile properties of SiC_w-Al₅₄₅₆ composites are computed varying the fiber's aspect ratio l/d , the fiber's volume fraction V_f and the representative element's aspect ratio L/D . The phase properties [3] are: Aluminium matrix(5456): $E = 73$ GPa, $\nu = 0.33$, $\sigma_{pl} = 241$ MPa (proportional limit), $\sigma_{0.2} = 259$ MPa (0.2% offset yield), and $n = 0.01$ (work hardening exponent); SiC_w: $E = 485$ GPa, $\nu = 0.2$.

1. COMPARISON OF THE PREDICTION OF GSCFEIAM WITH THE EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND THE PREDICTIONS OF PA MODEL

The comparison of the prediction of GSCFEIAM with the experimental results [3] and the predictions of two PA model [3] (one is the aligned fiber ends model, and the other is the staggered fiber ends model) for $l/d=L/D=4$ and $V_f=20\%$ is shown in Fig.2. It can be seen that the results of GSCFEIAM are consistent with the ones from the reference [3] in the elastic stage, while, in the plastic stage, the present results are between the ones of two fiber ends model, and agree with the experimental results well. In the present model, the effective medium is used to replace the "representative element's side wall constraint condition". Considering the two fiber ends models are two kinds of extreme cases of the unidirectional fiber array forms, and the fiber array forms in the present model are rather implicit, the results in Fig.2 are reasonable.

2. EFFECTS OF VARYING THE FIBER ASPECT RATIO AND VOLUME FRACTION ON THE OVERALL ELASTO-PLASTIC TENSILE PROPERTIES OF THE COMPOSITES

The values of the elastic modulus E , proportional limit σ_{pl} and the stress level σ_{iy} corresponding to the initial yield in the matrix of the composites with different fiber's aspect ratio and volume fraction calculated by GSCFEIAM and the experimental results [3] are presented in Table1.

Table 1. Comparison between testing results and prediction for SiCw-5456 composites

Volume% SiCw	Aspect ratio		E (GPa)		σ_{pl} (GPa)		σ_{iy} (MPa)
	l/d	L/D	Test	GSCFEIAM	Test	GSCFEIAM	GSCFEIAM
0	-	-	73	-	241	-	-
8%	4	4	88	92.0	220	226	185
12%	4	4	-	102.1	-	240	201
16%	4	4	-	112.6	-	255	215
20%	4	4	119	123.1	269	270	224
	3	4	-	125.5	-	260	220
	6	4	-	122.6	-	292	225
	1	1	106	100.5	241	245	204
	2	2	-	110.5	-	250	220
	8	8	-	136.1	-	323	251
	12	12	-	141.7	-	370	273
	16	16	-	144.8	-	392	282

The stress-strain curves of the composites for $V_f=20\%$ and $l/d=L/D=1,2,4,8,12,16$ are given in Fig.3, respectively. The elastic modulus E , proportional limit σ_{pl} , work-hardening rate n , and 0.2% offset yield $\sigma_{0.2}$ increase with increasing the fiber's aspect ratio. When l/d exceeds 16, the effects of fiber's aspect ratio are so faint that these cases can be disposed of as continuously fiber reinforced composites.

The stress-strain curves of the composites for $l/d=L/D=4$ and $V_f=8\%, 12\%, 16\% 20\%$ are given in Fig.4, respectively. The values of E , σ_{pl} , n and $\sigma_{0.2}$ also increase with increasing the fiber's volume fraction. For the case of $L/D=4$ and $V_f=8\%$ as shown in Fig.4 and Table1, it can be seen that the proportional limit of the composites is lower than the one of matrix. Papazian et al have ever got the same results from both experiment and theoretical prediction.

The definition of the proportional limit of the short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites should be different from the definition of its matrix. Because of the stress concentration, the matrix near fiber's ends yields quite early in the loading history. However, the presence of brittle fibers can constraint the propagation of plasticity, so in a succeeding loading stage, the slope of the stress-strain curve only deviates slightly. Therefore, we define the proportional limit of the composites as the stress level at which the slope of stress-strain curve deviates by 2% from the Young's modulus, which is adopted from the reference [3].

From the comparison of Fig.3 with Fig.4, it can be seen that the effects of varying the fiber's volume fraction on the overall properties of the composites are more drastic than the effects of varying the fiber's aspect ratio. But when the fiber's aspect ratio is small, for example, for $V_f=20\%$ and $l/d=1$ or 2 cases, the stress-strain curves are lower than that of $l/d=4$, $V_f=16\%$ case. This indicates that the overall properties of the short fiber reinforced composites are closely related to the microstructure of the composites. Therefore, the rule of mixture is not valid for predicting mechanical properties of the composites.

3. THE EFFECTS OF VARYING THE FIBER TO FIBER ENDS SPACING

The aspect ratio of representative element L/D can control the fiber to fiber ends spacing. The stress-strain curves for $V_f=20\%$ and $l/d=4$, while $L/D=3,4,16$ are shown in Fig.5, respectively. As it can be seen, the closer fiber to fiber ends spacing can increase the elastic modulus of the composites, but decrease the work-hardening rate.

4. THE DISTRIBUTION AND PROPAGATION OF THE PLASTIC REGION IN THE MATRIX

Studying the distribution and propagation of the plastic region in the matrix can further understand the elasto-plastic deformation behaviour of the composites. The initiation of plasticity and the propagation of the plastic region for $V_f=20\%$ and $L/D=l/d=4$ are show in Fig.6.

First, the matrix near the fiber's end yield quite early in the loading history, because of the stress concentration. And this corresponds to the stage that the slope of the stress-strain curve deviates faintly from the initial slope. Then the plastic region propagates mainly in the area between the fiber's ends and eventually, the plastic zones are interconnected. Macroscopically, the slope of the stress-strain curve drops rapidly and finally approaches a constant. In the end, the plastic region expands mainly in the area between the " fiber's side wall ". And, the composite exhibits characteristics of the succeeding strengthening.

From the preceding results and discussion, It can be seen that since the finite element method is employed, the physical model of the present method could accurately depict the phase geometrical configuration. In addition, for the brittle particles and whiskers reinforced ductile metal matrix composites, GSCFEIAM could derive explicit local stress and strain fields along with a detailed history of the initiation of plasticity and propagation of the plastic region in the matrix. And, the local stress and strain fields as well as the non-uniform plastic state are averaged to contribute to the overall properties of the composites. As a results, the microscopic representative element is united with the macroscopic composites concertedly. The comparison of the present results with the ones of experiment and PA models demonstrates the GSCFEIAM is effective.

The elasto-plastic behaviour of ductile metal is rather complicated because of the addition of brittle particles or whiskers. Macroscopically, the composites display a quite rich deformation process from the initiation of plasticity to succeeding strengthening. The corresponding stage in the stress - strain curve is rather smooth. Therefore, characterization of the stress-strain response in terms of 0.2% offset yield $\sigma_{0.2}$ is incomplete.

Generally speaking, increasing the fiber's aspect ratio and volume fraction causes very substantial increase of the values of the elastic modulus, proportional limit and work-hardening rate of the composites. And, the increasing extent depends on the ability of the fibers to constraint the plastic deformation of the matrix. For the small fiber's volume fraction case, e.g. $V_f=8\%$, such ability is so weak that the initial plasticity produced by the stress concentration could rapidly propagate in the matrix and this results in the proportional limit of the composites being lower than the one of the matrix.

CONCLUSION

1. GSCFEIAM could effectively predict the overall elasto-plastic properties of short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites. Its results are between the ones of two PA models and consistent with the experimental results well.
2. GSCFEIAM could dispose of the nonlinear problems of the composites containing complicated microstructure, and could describe the detailed local stress and strain fields of each phase of the composite.
3. Increasing the fiber's aspect ratio and volume fraction. generally, can increase the elastic modulus, proportional limit and work-hardening rate of the composites. If the fiber's aspect ratio exceeds 16, the stress-strain curves of such composites approach the one of continuous fiber reinforced composites. For the small fiber's volume fraction case, the proportional limit of the composite might be lower than the one of the matrix.
4. Characterization of the stress-strain response in terms of 0.2% offset yield $\sigma_{0.2}$ is incomplete. It is influenced by the proportional limit and initial work-hardening rate.
5. The propagation of the plastic region between the fibers in the matrix affects remarkably the elasto-plastic behaviour of the composites.
6. The closer fiber to fiber ends spacing would increase the elastic modulus of the composites, but decrease the work-hardening rate.

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Figure 1. Finite-element mesh for GSCFEIAM. Representative element enlarged

Figure 2. Comparison of the prediction of GSCFEIAM with the ones of PA models, $l/d = 4$, and the testing results for 20% SiCw- Al₅₄₅₆

Figure 3. Effects of varying fiber aspect ratio, l/d , on the composite tensile properties for 20% SiCw- Al₅₄₅₆

Figure 4. Effects of varying the volume fraction of SiCw, $l/d = L/D = 4$, on the composite tensile properties for SiCw- Al₅₄₅₆

Figure 5. Effects of varying the fiber to fiber ends spacing on the composite tensile properties for 20% SiCw- Al₅₄₅₆

Figure 5 distribution and propagation of the plastic region in the matrix for ($l/d = L/D = 4$) 20% SiC_w-Al₃Si₆